

Antibody Characterization Report for Ubiquilin-2

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Ubiquilin-2

Alternative protein name: Chap1, DSK2 homolog, Protein linking IAP with cytoskeleton 2

Gene name: *UBQLN2*

Uniprot: Q9UHD9

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Ubiquilin-2. We used an antibody characterization pipeline [2] based on knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for Ubiquilin-2 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. An HAP1 *UBQLN2* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Ubiquilin-2 in HAP1 is adequate as determined by searching DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the Ubiquilin-2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry/Addgene)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab190283*	GR3297673-4	AB_2747782	monoclonal	6H9	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF
ABclonal	A9568	92790201	AB_2772790	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.42	Wb,IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP59353	QC30343-40589	AB_10865653	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-technie	NBP2-25164*	81919	AB_2885154	monoclonal	6H9	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	85509**	1	AB_2800056	recombinant-mono	D7R2Z	rabbit	0.12	Wb,IP
Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank	PCRP-UBQLN2-1C7*	2021-03-04	AB_2619216	monoclonal	PCRP-UBQLN2-1C7	mouse	0.03	Wb,IP
Proteintech	23449-1-AP	52217	AB_2879282	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.55	Wb,IF
Structural Genomics Consortium	Z-UBQLN2-7**	YSUBQLN2A-c001	Addgene_166563	recombinant-mono	YSUBQLN2A-c001	human	0.65	IP
Thermo Fisher Scientific	35-4400*	WA320043	AB_2533204	monoclonal	3B8A10	mouse	0.50	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	37-7700*	VA300207	AB_2533341	monoclonal	3D5E2	mouse	0.50	Wb,IP,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC004089c001	CVCL_TW09	HAP1	UBQLN2 KO

Figure 1: Ubiquilin-2 antibody screening by immunoblot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *UBQLN2* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for immunoblot with the indicated Ubiquilin-2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab190283* at 1/2000, A9568 at 1/1000, ARP59353 at 1/500, NBP2-25164* at 1/2000, 85509** at 1/1000, PCRP-UBQLN2-1C7* at 1/26, 23449-1-AP at 1/1000, Z-UBQLN2-7** at 1/653, 35-4400* at 1/1000, and 37-7700* at 1/2000. Predicted band size: 65 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Ubiquilin-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Ubiquilin-2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein G or protein A or Flag-M2 magnetic beads. Samples were washed and processed for immunoblot with the indicated Ubiquilin-2 antibody. For immunoblot, 85509** was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: Ubiquilin-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *UBQLN2* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with glass bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated Ubiquilin-2 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibody dilution used: ab190283* at 1/1000, A9568 at 1/2000, ARP59353 at 1/500, NBP2-25164* at 1/1000, 85509** at 1/200, PCRP-UBQLN2-1C7* at 1/20, 23449-1-AP at 1/300, Z-UBQLN2-7** at 1/600, 35-4400* at 1/500, and 37-7700* at 1/500. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 1: Ubiquitin-2 antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Ubiquitin-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: Ubiquilin-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: Ubiquilin-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested Ubiquilin-2 antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 62-6520 and 65-6120). Peroxidase-conjugated monoclonal anti-Flag M2 is from MilliporeSigma (cat. number A8592). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21424 and A21429).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by immunoblot

Immunoblots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [4]. HAP1 WT and *UBQLN2* KO were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and immunoblot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Immunoblots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual immunoblot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% bovine serum albumin in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively), or anti-Flag M2 magnetic beads from MilliporeSigma (cat. number M8823). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates are rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and immunoblot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX).

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. HAP1 WT and *UBQLN2* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in 96 well glass plates (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Ubiquilin-2 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro widefield high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.45 air immersion objective and scientific CMOS camera, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (Lumencor Aura III light engine)

and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa568 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns. Three images per field were acquired at a z-interval of 4 microns. Then, best focus intensity projections were generated from the z-stack. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

References

1. Laflamme, C., et al., *Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies*. N Biotechnol, 2021. **65**: p. 1-8 DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001.
2. Laflamme, C., et al., *Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72*. Elife, 2019. **8** DOI: 10.7554/eLife.48363.
3. Ghandi, M., et al., *Next-generation characterization of the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia*. Nature, 2019. **569**(7757): p. 503-508 DOI: 10.1038/s41586-019-1186-3.
4. Ayoubi, R., P.S. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody Screening by Immunoblot*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717510>.
5. Ayoubi, R., et al., *Antibody screening by Immunoprecipitation*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717516>.
6. Alshafie, W., P. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody screening by Immunofluorescence*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717498>.